

Introductory Editorial

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Editorial Introduction to the First Issue

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On behalf of the Board, I am delighted to announce the launch of the inaugural issue of the first journal dedicated to the North African countries and Mediterranean region "*The North African Journal of Food and Nutrition Research (NAJFNR)*". A new open access and international peer-reviewed journal, which publishes original (not previously published) work of exceptional quality and interest and which intends to give a wide-ranging coverage of research, views, and reviews on nutrition and its effects in relation to human health and disease. The *NAJFNR* will include all nutrition field research in humans and various disease model organisms and will be of interest to the basic researcher as well as to physician scientists and clinicians.

Eleven (11) main specialties are involved:

- Effect of nutrition on metabolic control;
- Epidemiology, and the prevalence of related disorders such as obesity, diabetes, dyslipidemias, etc.;
- Biochemistry and cellular metabolism of nutrients;
- Dietary strategies;
- Food Security and Challenges;
- Food behavior and quality of life;
- Public Health Policy & Health Economics;
- Nutrition and Cancer;
- Food Chemistry;
- Clinical Nutrition;
- Food Processing and Packaging.

The *NAJFNR* will be published both in print and online with an option for open access. All articles will be promptly peer-reviewed by leading experts. We expect *NAJFNR* to attract manuscripts of the highest quality in order to be of the greatest possible benefit to its readers.

In this journal, we offer an opportunity for scientists across various disciplines in human nutrition and metabolism to share their knowledge and expertise to a wider range of audience. All articles will be accessible without any access boundaries to all internet users worldwide. The journal will certainly be competing head-on with a number of existing subscription based journals but clearly there is a niche for this new journal.

The *NAJFNR* is following the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors (ICJME) recommendations <http://www.icmje.org/journals-following-the-icmje-recommendations/#N> and is under the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license (CC BY 4.0).

Pr. Khaled M.B.

Editor-in-Chief and Founder

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